

BRINGING THE POWER OF KamAZ DIESEL ENGINES OPERATED BY IN MOUNTAINOUS CONDITIONS TO STANDARD ATMOSPHERIC CONDITIONS

Mirgani Fayziev¹

¹Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract. The article presents correction coefficients that take into account changes in barometric pressure by 1 kPa in the range from 60 to 105 kPa to supplement GOST 14846-81 and based on the results of tests of the KamAZ-5320 car in mountainous conditions with a nominal load of 8 tons on different gearbox gears, formulas have been developed to bring the power of KamAZ diesel engines to standard atmospheric conditions [1, 2].

For carburetor engines, a number of fairly accurate reduction formulas are known, included in GOST and in the standards of foreign countries. Unlike carburetor engines, in which changes in atmospheric conditions mainly affect the amount of mixture entering the engine, in diesels it is also reflected in the composition of the mixture, characterized by an excess air coefficient [3]. Indeed, the change in diesels is more significant compared to a carburetor engine, which significantly affects the dynamics of the cycle and, consequently, the engine workflow. Therefore, in order to bring the effective performance of diesel to any atmospheric conditions, the features of a particular engine must be taken into account [8].

Introduction. The tests of the KamAZ-740 engine in real mountain conditions during traffic showed that in order to bring diesel power to normal atmospheric conditions according to GOST 14846-81 [1], it is possible to use reduction formulas only up to a height of 1200 m above sea level or with a change in barometric pressure in the range from 88 to 105 kPa (660 760 mm Hg. art.). Since the tests were carried out up to a height of 4200 m above sea level and the pressure decreased to 60 kPa, it is necessary to develop a new analytical form of the formula for bringing the obtained experimental data into agreement.

It should be noted that the studies carried out so far and the developed reduction formulas, in addition to work [4], are valid only for bench conditions, and they cannot be recommended for real operating conditions. It is known that the operation of engines in mountainous conditions differs significantly from the conditions of laboratory tests, even when simulating the rarefaction of air. In full-scale conditions, numerous factors act in a complex manner, since solar radiation, temperature and pressure, air density, fuel temperature, etc. change simultaneously.

Analysis of existing formulas shows that when operating engines without supercharging, it is generally accepted that the average indicator pressure and indicator power (at $n = const$) are proportional to the amount of air in the cylinder, i.e. the air-fuel ratio remains unchanged [13]. This group includes national standards of a number of countries, (SAE data, etc.):

$$N_e = N_{eo} \cdot \frac{\rho_e}{\rho_{eo}}, \quad g_e = g_{eo} \cdot \frac{\rho_{eo}}{\rho_e}, \quad (1)$$

where N_e, g_e, ρ_e - respectively, the engine power, specific fuel consumption and air density obtained during the tests;

$N_{eo}, g_{eo}, \rho_{eo}$ - accordingly, the engine power, specific fuel consumption and air density are reduced to standard atmospheric conditions;

as well as the reduction formulas recommended by GOST 10448-80. The difference is that the latter take into account the influence of atmospheric humidity on the partial pressure of water vapor contained in this air.

$$g_e = g_{eo} \cdot \frac{\rho_{eo}}{\rho_e} \quad (2)$$

where p_o, T_o , Then is the pressure and temperature of atmospheric air under standard atmospheric conditions;

p_B – intake air pressure.

Research methodology. In the formulas of this group, an $\alpha = \text{const}$ assumption is made that the friction power of the engine changes in the same way as the indicator power, i.e. directly proportional to the density of the air ρ_g . At the same time, according to many researchers [2, 11], the friction power depends very little on the pressure and temperature of atmospheric air. The results of testing the KamAZ-5320 car in mountainous conditions confirmed that, indeed, the friction power changed very little in these conditions.

The second group includes formulas in which changes in power and specific fuel consumption occur according to a different law, i.e. are not directly proportional to the ratio of air density (formulas of the US Electrical Engineering Commission, Kova and Green, A.I.Zaikin). In these formulas, an attempt has been made to correct inaccuracies made in the formulas of the first group. The formula of academician V.V.Mahaldiani [9] is more perfect, where mechanical losses and the coefficient of excess air α are taken into account. They used the experimental data of Prof. T.M. Melkumov and A.N.Tolstov, indicating the rectilinear nature of the dependence:

$$\eta_i / \alpha = f(\alpha) \quad \eta_i / \alpha = f(\alpha); \quad N_e = \frac{N_{eo}}{\eta_{mo}} \left[\eta_{mo} + \kappa + \kappa(1 - \kappa) \cdot 288\alpha_o - 1 \right], \quad (3)$$

where $\kappa = \frac{p}{p_o} \sqrt{\frac{T_o}{T}}$

η_{mo}, α_o – the mechanical efficiency of the diesel engine and the excess air coefficient, reduced to standard atmospheric conditions.

This formula is valid for naturally aspirated diesels tested in bench conditions.

G.A.Khantadze proposed a formula that takes into account the effect of air pressure on the friction power [12]:

$$N_e = N_{eo} \left[\frac{1-a}{\eta_{mo}} \cdot \kappa - \left(\frac{1-a}{\eta_{mo}} - 1 \right) \right], \quad (4)$$

where $a = (1 - \epsilon)(1 - \eta_{mo})$; (a, ϵ – empirical coefficients).

It should be noted that formula (3) closely coincides with the formula of Prof. F. Schmidt [14]. F. Schmidt's formula is valid for reducing the parameters of a naturally aspirated diesel engine to standard atmospheric conditions for the case when $\alpha = \text{const}$, assuming that $g_i = \text{const}$. At the same time, the main influencing factor remains the hourly air consumption (G_g).

$$N_e = N_{eo} \left[\kappa + B(\kappa - 1) \left(\frac{1}{\eta_{mo}} - 1 \right) \right], \quad (5)$$

where $\kappa = \frac{N_i^*}{N_{io}} = \left(\frac{T_o}{T^*} \right)^m \cdot \left(\frac{B - \varphi P_n}{B_o - \varphi_o P_{no}} \right)$

(B - atmospheric air pressure; p - saturation pressure of water vapor; φ - relative humidity of the air). Equation (5) served as the basis of the German standard DIN 6170 and was used to determine the power of carburetor and diesel engines without supercharging for various heights above sea level. In 1961, the formula was recommended by the Congress of the International Ice Council (SIMAC) for practical use. Also, the SIMAC Congress proposed the following dependencies as reduction formulas before 1971:

$$N_e^* = N_{eo} \left[\kappa - 0,7(1 - \kappa) \left(\frac{1}{\eta_{mo}} - 1 \right) \right], \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } \kappa = \frac{N_i^*}{N_{io}} = \left(\frac{B - \varphi P_n}{B_o - \varphi_o P_{no}} \right)^u \cdot \left(\frac{T_o}{T^*} \right)^v \cdot \left(\frac{T_{wo}}{T_w} \right)^q$$

(T_w - is the absolute temperature of the cooling water at the inlet to the air cooler). The values of other indicators $u = 0.7$; $v = 1.2 \div 2.0$ and $q = 0 \div 1.2$ depend on the type of boost. The specific fuel consumption is determined from the expression:

$$g_e^* = \frac{\kappa}{\alpha} \cdot g_{eo}, \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where } \kappa = \frac{p}{p_o} \sqrt{\frac{T_o}{T}},$$

Good convergence of the results is ensured when the ambient air pressure changes. These formulas use a number of assumptions that limit their universality. At the same time, they differ in simplicity. The CMEA 4394-83 standard applies to four-stroke diesels. The formulas in it have the following form:

$$N_e^* = N_{eo} \left[\kappa - 0,7(1 - \kappa) \left(\frac{1}{\eta_{mo}} - 1 \right) \right] \cdot \Delta;$$

$$\kappa = \left(\frac{B - p_n}{748} \right)^m \cdot \left(\frac{293}{T^*} \right)^n \cdot \left(\frac{T_{wo}}{T_w} \right)^q \quad (8)$$

Results of research and discussion. The values m , n and q depend on the excess air coefficient and are assumed to be constant at separate intervals of change α . It should be noted that these formulas are more advanced, because they take into account the change in fuel density (multiplier Δ), as well as the initial value of the excess air coefficient. Thanks to this approach α , the formula takes into account the influence more fully, although the stepwise dependence of the indicators m , n and q on α can serve as a source of error. In addition, this formula is valid only when testing engines in bench conditions [4]. In the formulas of the second group, assumptions are made that the mass charge of the cylinder in a diesel engine changes proportionally to the air temperature, which is not confirmed by the research of Prof. D.A.Portnov [11] and our tests. It can be assumed that in mountainous conditions, the filling coefficient of the KamAZ-740 diesel engine changes very little with changes in air temperature, and air pressure remains the main factor. The third group includes formulas developed comprehensively and generically. These are the formulas of Prof. D.A.Portnov and S.I.Pogodin, Prof. I.Ya.Dzhebashvili, Prof. S.M.Kadyrov and GOST 14846-81 [1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14].

S.M.Kadyrov proposed a formula for bringing the indicators of YAMZ-236 diesel engines with and without supercharging, which characterizes the testing of engines in full-scale operating conditions. He also obtained generalized coefficients for two types of diesel engines:

Diesel without supercharging

$$K_{N_e} = \left(\frac{p}{p_o} \right)^{0.9} \cdot \left(\frac{T_o}{T} \right)^{0.57}$$

$$K_{g_e} = \left(\frac{p_o}{p} \right)^{0.9} \cdot \left(\frac{T}{T_o} \right)^{0.64} \quad (9)$$

Supercharged diesel

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_{N_e} &= \left(\frac{p}{p_o}\right)^{0.9} \cdot \left(\frac{T_o}{T}\right)^{0.264} \\
 K_{g_e} &= \left(\frac{p_o}{p}\right)^{0.9} \cdot \left(\frac{T}{T_o}\right)^{0.264}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{10}$$

Formula (9) for the case without supercharging has some convergence with the results of testing the KamAZ-5320 car in mountainous conditions. In this regard, when carrying out the power of KamAZ-740 diesels to normal atmospheric conditions, it is necessary to take formula (9) as a basis with clarification of their degrees.

According to GOST 14846-81, the influence of external operating conditions on diesel performance is taken into account using reduction coefficients $K_{N_e}, K_{G_T}, K_{g_e}$. The correction values for four-stroke diesel engines without supercharging and turbocharged correspond to a change in atmospheric pressure in the range from 88 to 105 kPa. In our case, the tests were carried out at an altitude of up to 4200 m above sea level, the change in air pressure does not comply with GOST. Therefore, in order to bring the effective performance of the KamAZ-740 engine to normal atmospheric conditions, it is necessary to find correction coefficients that take into account the change in barometric pressure values by 1 kPa in the range from 60 to 88 kPa, and from 88 to 105 kPa to use GOST 14846-81, which provides quite satisfactory convergence of the calculation and experiment results.

In general, the following formulas are proposed for bringing the power and specific effective fuel consumption for KamAZ-740 diesels to standard conditions:

$$N_{eo} = \frac{N_e}{K_{N_e}} ; \quad g_{eo} = \frac{g_e}{K_{g_e}}
 \tag{11}$$

The index "o" indicates the values of values under normal atmospheric conditions.

As a result of computational and theoretical studies, the following formulas are proposed for bringing the effective performance of the KamAZ-740 engine to normal atmospheric conditions:

$$N_e = N_{eo} \left(\frac{p}{p_o}\right)^{0.75} \cdot \left(\frac{T_o}{T}\right)^{0.57} ,
 \tag{12}$$

$$g_e = g_{eo} \left(\frac{p_o}{p}\right)^{0.75} \cdot \left(\frac{T}{T_o}\right)^{0.64} .
 \tag{13}$$

Fig.1. The effect of terrain altitude above sea level on the performance of the KamAZ-740 diesel engine at $n = 2600 \text{ min}^{-1}$ ____ experiment; ____ calculation

Conclusions. According to the test results obtained and the formulas developed (12 and 13), correction coefficients are proposed for the operational test conditions, taking into account changes in barometric pressure by 1 kPa in the range from 60 to 105 kPa to supplement GOST 14846-81 with them. These coefficients are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Conditions for applying the correction factor	Height above sea level, m	The value of the correction K_v , 1/kPa
When changing the B_{env} in the range:		
from 88 to 105 kPa	1200 ÷ 0	0,0072
from 78 to 88 kPa	2200 ÷ 1200	0,0075
from 69 to 78 kPa	3200 ÷ 2200	0,0078
from 60 to 69 kPa	4200 ÷ 3200	0,0081

A comparison of the calculation and experimental results for the KamAZ-740 engine is of some scientific interest (see Fig.1). As can be seen from the figure, the proposed equations provide convergence from 1 to 3% and shows their great acceptability for engineering calculations and practical application.

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